

New European Bauhaus Call for proposals for Citizen Engagement Activities

Project Acronym: SOCIAL4FOOD

**Project title: SOCIAL farming FOR stimulating transgenerational knowledge
transfer and production of typical local FOOD**

Deliverable 5.1: Results of Qualitative survey

30th November 2022

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1. Executive summary

The SOCIAL4FOOD project aims to apply the New European Bauhaus principles to improve the contact between young generations and green public spaces, guided by the wisdom of the elders. Through a series of social farming activities, the project aims to stimulate the involvement of teenagers from the Town of Arsoli (including also young immigrants) in collaboratively farming and cooking a very ancient and high-quality bean typical of this town, named “fagiolina arsolana”.

The main purpose of this deliverable is to provide a comprehensive description of the results of the qualitative survey administered to participants of the SOCIAL4FOOD activities for feedback and possible refinements.

2. The survey

The survey consisted of two questionnaires (one for adults and adolescents and one for children) and an interview. The questionnaires contained a mixture of different items ranging from multiple-choice to Likert-type scales and in some cases provided respondents with the opportunity for free expression. All participants in the SOCIAL4FOOD activities were invited to respond to the questionnaires. Participation in the study was voluntary, and informed consent for participants under 18 years old was obtained by their parents before the questionnaire administration began. To ensure consistency, the questionnaires were designed and printed in the Italian language. The interview was conducted in Italian and administered to the four representatives of the four social entities involved in the project (the Mayor of Arsoli, President of the social elderly centre of Arsoli, President of Pro Loco of Arsoli, President of the Association of local producers “Amici della fagiolina di Arsoli”).

In the following sub-sections, a brief description of the structure of the two questionnaires and the interview are given.

2.1. Questionnaires for adults and adolescents

The questionnaire for adults and adolescents consists of 19 items grouped under four different sections, plus a preliminary and an introductory section. The preliminary section comprises elicited personal information of respondents including age and gender, while the introductory section contains questions aimed to analyse the participant's expectations, learned contents, and addressed topics. In Section I, questions sought the perception about the organisation of the events (green social laboratories, SOCIAL4FOOD Competition, and co-creation events) in terms of duration, number, and location. In Section II, a self-evaluation of the acquired knowledge and abilities and the satisfaction with the process and the shared solution of the social farm is analysed. Section III contains questions about the events in terms of usefulness, difficulties, acquired knowledge, and participants' collaboration. Finally, in Section IV, participants are asked to express their general satisfaction with the project activities. Adults and adolescents participating in the SOCIAL4FOOD activities were invited to respond to the questionnaire either using a paper form or an online form

(https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfyVeYEZdb_ezV_FLh_E-rM7quVa4YfiWLDdjOBiftTO-VFXQ/viewform?usp=sf_link). The paper form of the questionnaire for adults and adolescents is provided in the Appendix A.

2.2. Questionnaires for children

The questionnaire for children consists of 12 items grouped under four different sections, plus an introductory section. The introductory section contains questions aimed to analyse the children's satisfaction with the project activities. In Section I, questions sought the perception of the events (green social laboratories and SOCIAL4FOOD Competition) in terms of amusement. Section II contains questions about the organization of the events (duration and number). In Section III, a self-evaluation of the acquired knowledge and perceived

difficulties is analysed. Finally, in Section IV, children are asked to express their general satisfaction with the project activities. The questionnaire for children is provided in Appendix B.

2.3. Interview for representatives

The interview schedule consisted of 5 questions investigating the advantages, difficulties, and replicability of the project's results. In the following table the questions are provided:

Question A	What is your overall opinion on the Social4Food project?
Question B	What are the benefits of the project to the community of Arsoli?
Question C	Have you encountered any negative aspects or difficulties in carrying out the project activities? If so, what could be improved?
Question D	Do you think it is appropriate to repeat the project activities in the following years?
Question E	Do you think the results obtained from the project can be applied to neighboring local communities?

3. Results of the survey

This Section discusses the results of both the questionnaires and the interviews.

The return of the questionnaires amounted to 72 respondents (21 children and 51 adults and adolescents), which formed a base for the quantitative analysis. In the following sub-sections, the results of each questionnaire and responses to the interview are discussed in detail.

3.1. Results of questionnaires for adults and adolescents

The questionnaire was filled in by 51 respondents (35 women and 16 men), which 2 adolescents, 40 people with age 19-59, and 9 elderly people. In the following, results are analyzed according to the six sections that have been introduced in Section 2.1.

The participant's expectations of the project activities have been satisfied for most respondents (51%). Learned contents were already known by most of the respondents (49%) who wanted to deepen them, while the addressed topics have been sufficiently thorough for all the respondents.

Considering the organisation of the events, the number, duration, and location of the events fully satisfied all the respondents. New knowledge and abilities have been acquired by all participants (41% of respondents stated to have acquired enough knowledge), mainly in the use of the fagiolina for preparing salty and sweet recipes.

Participation in the co-creation events has been considered very useful for sharing ideas (35%) and actively contributing to the co-creation of the social farm (35%). The shared solution on the management and organization of the social farm satisfied all participants.

The green social laboratories, SOCIAL4FOOD competition, and co-creation events have been considered very interesting (59% of respondents), and the majority (59%) already could apply the acquired knowledge by preparing the recipes learnt during the laboratories. No difficulties to perform the proposed activities have been encountered by all participants, who also underlined a very positive participants' collaboration.

Finally, a high level of general satisfaction with the project activities resulted from the answers (41% of respondents), as well as a good level of usefulness in re-proposing the activities in the next years (51% of respondents).

3.2. Results of questionnaires for children

The questionnaire was filled in by 21 children. In the following, results are analyzed according to the four sections that have been introduced in Section 2.2.

A high level of children's satisfaction with the project activities resulted from the analysed responses all children enjoyed all the proposed activities. All the children had fun during the laboratories and culinary challenge. The most appreciated laboratory (71%) was the cooking one, while during the culinary challenge, children had the most fun preparing the hand-made pasta (67%) and sauce (33%) with their friends. Only 14% of children indicated the least appreciated activity that is the slide presentation illustrating the activity implementation.

All the children would like to participate in a greater number of laboratories and challenges and considered adequate the available time for the activity implementation.

No difficulties to perform the proposed activities have been encountered by all children. New knowledge and abilities have been acquired by all participants, mainly in the use of the fagiolina for preparing traditional recipes (76%).

Finally, all children appreciated the opportunity to have a social farm for growing the fagiolina together with their friends, elderly people, and local farmers. All children underlined a very positive collaboration both with their friends and elderly people.

3.3. Results of the interview

The interviews were transcribed and translated into the English language.

Question A	Mayor of Arsoli: It was a very interesting project that involved various target groups from children to elders and created a very important synergy among the municipal administration, the Association of local producers and the Pro Loco of Arsoli.
	President of Social elderly center of Arsoli: Very positive because local traditions must be handed down in order not to be lost.
	President of Pro Loco of Arsoli: The project has reawakened the interest in the "fagiolina arsolana", a very ancient product that the Pro Loco, local associations and the Municipality of Arsoli have been promoting for some

	<p>time. I believe that the project was significant because it drew even more attention to this typical bean</p> <p>President of the Association of local producers “Amici della fagiolina di Arsoli”: Positive. Projects like this allow stimulating the population and mainly young people to hand down the culture and traditions of Arsoli.</p>
Question B	<p>Mayor of Arsoli: The greatest benefit was the involvement of the population which allowed for greater attention from citizens to this typical product.</p> <p>President of the Social elderly centre of Arsoli: The project supported and promoted the activities necessary to carry on the tradition of this typical product.</p> <p>President of Pro Loco of Arsoli: The project attracted the attention of children and adolescents, the less involved groups in the past experiences, on whom it is necessary to work for carrying on the tradition of the fagiolina arsolana.</p> <p>President of the Association of local producers “Amici della fagiolina di Arsoli”: The benefits will be long-term because making children interact with elderly people, who keep the knowledge of the cultivation techniques, means “sowing” the culture and the sense of belonging to the territory. That allows the tradition of this typical product, which has been produced in Arsoli for over 500 years, to be handed down.</p>
Question C	<p>Mayor of Arsoli: Everything went swimmingly thanks to the support of the municipal administration, the Association of local producers and the Pro Loco of Arsoli, who were ready to welcome the benefits of the project.</p> <p>President of Social elderly centre of Arsoli: Everything went well, it was a constructive project.</p> <p>President of Pro Loco of Arsoli: No, I cannot find any negative aspects because the project activities have been implemented in a very professional way. The difficulties were not related to the project but to the post-lockdown climate which made it very difficult to involve people.</p> <p>President of the Association of local producers “Amici della fagiolina di Arsoli”: There were no negative aspects, it was a pleasure to collaborate with the children and adolescents. The social entities of our area, such as schools, could be more involved to give more value to the project results.</p>
Question D	<p>Mayor of Arsoli: Handing down the knowledge and popular culture is an important part of the project that must be replicated. In this regard, we are signing a collaboration agreement among the municipal administration, the association of local producers, the Pro Loco, and the social elderly centre.</p> <p>President of Social elderly centre of Arsoli: Sure, it is important to replicate the activities of the project to pass on the tradition to everyone.</p> <p>President of Pro Loco of Arsoli: I think it was a positive experience. The round tables and collaborative activities allowed the exchange of new ideas that should be replicated in the next years.</p>

	President of the Association of local producers “Amici della fagiolina di Arsoli”: It is important to continue the project activities to create new opportunities for young people.
Question E	Mayor of Arsoli: The towns in our area are rich in typical products and local traditions linked to a peasant culture that can be fostered. In this regard, the mayors of neighbouring municipalities were invited to the final event of the project.
	President of Social elderly centre of Arsoli: It is important to make the tradition of the fagiolina arsolana known to all the neighbouring towns.
	President of Pro Loco of Arsoli: The project results should be applied to the neighbouring municipalities. However, this is very difficult, as underlined by similar experiences we had in the past. It is important to try again, involving children and adolescents also with the help of the schools.
	President of the Association of local producers “Amici della fagiolina di Arsoli”: From an agro-food point of view, our territory is rich in typical products that should be stimulated because they can represent an excellent opportunity for work and social growth.

A word cloud giving a graphical representation of the prominence of words that appeared more frequently in the interviews with the 4 representatives of social entities is shown in the following figure. The larger the word in the visual graph the more common the word was in the interviews.

The words mentioned most by interviewees are "project", "Arsoli", "Tradition" and "Typical". This finding does conform to the aim of the project to focus on the typical local food and tradition of Arsoli town.

A high relevance is also given to the target audience of the project: "children", "municipal", "young", "adolescents", "people" and "ProLoco" reflect that the project allows involving the entire community of Arsoli.

Another much mentioned word is "positive" underlying a positive opinion of the interviewees on the project outcomes.

Appendix A

Questionario di gradimento delle attività del progetto SOCIAL4FOOD – adulti e adolescenti

Con il seguente questionario, rigorosamente anonimo, vogliamo rilevare il grado di soddisfazione dei partecipanti alle attività del progetto SOCIAL4FOOD. Ti invitiamo a rispondere alle domande, segnando la risposta per te più rispondente o almeno più vicina alle tue opinioni.

GENERE

- maschio femmina altro

FASCIA D'ETA

- 14-18
- 19-59
- da 60 in su

PARTE INTRODUTTIVA

- Rispetto alle aspettative che avevi prima di partecipare alle attività del progetto SOCIAL4FOOD, queste sono state confermate?

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco

per niente

- I contenuti appresi durante le attività del progetto:

erano già di tua conoscenza

non erano di tua conoscenza

erano in parte di tua conoscenza, ma desideravi approfondirli

- Le tematiche affrontate:

sono state sufficientemente approfondite

non sono state sufficientemente approfondite. Perché?

le attività sono durate troppo poco per approfondire le tematiche

(altro)

PARTE I: ORGANIZZAZIONE

- Ritieni che il numero degli eventi organizzati (laboratori, sfida culinaria ed eventi di co-creazione) sia stato adeguato?

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco
per niente

Se hai risposto poco o per niente, pensi che il numero degli eventi doveva essere

maggiore minore

Commento_____

- Ritieni che la durata degli eventi organizzati (laboratori, sfida culinaria ed eventi di co-creazione) sia stata adeguata?

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco
per niente

Se hai risposto poco o per niente, pensi che la durata degli eventi doveva essere

maggiore minore

Commento_____

- Giudichi adeguati gli ambienti offerti per lo svolgimento degli eventi organizzati (laboratori, sfida culinaria ed eventi di co-creazione)?

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco
per niente

Commento_____

PARTE II: AUTOVALUTAZIONE

- Partecipando ai laboratori e alla sfida culinaria hai acquisito

nuove conoscenze:

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco
per niente

nuove abilità:

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco
per niente

- Che tipo di conoscenze hai acquisito?
-

- Che tipo di abilità hai acquisito?
-

- Partecipando agli eventi di co-creazione, li hai ritenuti utili per condividere le tue idee?

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco
per niente

Se hai risposto poco o per niente, cosa suggerisci per migliorare?

- Partecipando agli eventi di co-creazione, pensi di avere contribuito attivamente alla co-creazione dell'orto sociale?
 - moltissimo molto abbastanza
 poco per niente

Se hai risposto poco o per niente, cosa suggerisci per migliorare?

- Quanto ti soddisfa la soluzione proposta per gestire ed organizzare l'orto sociale?
 - moltissimo molto abbastanza poco
per niente

Se hai risposto poco o per niente, che cosa non ti soddisfa?

PARTE III: VALUTAZIONE DEGLI EVENTI ORGANIZZATI

- Gli eventi organizzati (laboratori, sfida culinaria ed eventi di co-creazione) sono stati interessanti?

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco

per niente

Se hai risposto poco o per niente, cosa suggerisci per migliorare?

- Le conoscenze che hai acquisito durante gli eventi organizzati (laboratori, sfida culinaria ed eventi di co-creazione) sono state utili?

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco

per niente

- Sei riuscito a mettere in pratica le conoscenze che hai acquisito durante gli eventi organizzati (laboratori, sfida culinaria ed eventi di co-creazione)?

Sì No

Se hai risposto sì, come?

- Hai incontrato difficoltà nello svolgere le attività proposte negli eventi organizzati (laboratori, sfida culinaria ed eventi di co-creazione)?

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco

per niente

Se hai risposto moltissimo, molto o abbastanza, quali difficoltà hai incontrato?

- Durante gli eventi organizzati (laboratori, sfida culinaria ed eventi di co-creazione) si è creato un clima di partecipazione positivo?

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco

per niente

Se hai risposto poco o per niente, cosa suggerisci per migliorare?

PARTE IV: SODDISFAZIONE GENERALE

- Quanto sei soddisfatto delle attività svolte negli eventi organizzati (laboratori, sfida culinaria ed eventi di co-creazione)?

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco
per niente

- Quanto pensi sia opportuno riproporre le attività negli anni successivi?

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco
per niente

Ti ringraziamo per la collaborazione

Appendix B

Questionario di gradimento delle attività del progetto SOCIAL4FOOD - bambini

Ti chiediamo di rispondere alle domande che trovi di seguito.

PARTE INTRODUTTIVA

- Ti è piaciuta questa esperienza sulla fagiolina arsolana?

- Ti piacerebbe rifare nei prossimi anni esperienze simili?

PARTE I: VALUTAZIONE DEGLI EVENTI ORGANIZZATI

Durante il progetto sono stati organizzati 3 laboratori (sulla coltivazione, sulla cucina e sulla raccolta della fagiolina) e una sfida di cucina.

- Ti sei divertito durante i laboratori?

- Quale è la cosa che ti ha divertito di più?

- E quella che ti ha divertito di meno?

- Ti sei divertito durante la sfida di cucina?

- Quale è la cosa che ti ha divertito di più?
-

- E quella che ti ha divertito di meno?
-

PARTE II: ORGANIZZAZIONE

- Avresti voluto partecipare ad un numero maggiore di laboratori?

- Avresti voluto partecipare ad un numero maggiore di sfide?

- Il tempo che hai avuto a disposizione per svolgere le attività è stato sufficiente?

PARTE III: AUTOVALUTAZIONE

- Hai incontrato delle difficoltà durante i laboratori?

- Quali difficoltà hai incontrato?
-

- Pensi di aver imparato qualcosa di nuovo sulla fagiolina arsolana?

- Che cosa hai imparato?
-

PARTE IV: SODDISFAZIONE GENERALE

- Ti piacerebbe avere a disposizione un orto dove svolgere attività insieme ai tuoi compagni, alla scuola, agli anziani e agli agricoltori?

- Ti sei trovato/a bene con gli altri bambini e bambine?

- Ti è piaciuto stare insieme agli anziani ed imparare da loro?

GRAZIE